

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC BASICS OF TEACHING OTHER LANGUAGE TO CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The language is a product of social relations, and the native language of every people living in our country is a vivid indicator of their national identity and spiritual culture. Language forms consciousness, being monadically connected with thinking. The connection of speech and thinking is manifested not only at the deep stages of psychological processes, but also at the level of social phenomena. The influence that the word has on a person, on his behavior, is well known to everyone.

Currently, there are two principles in the interaction between languages in our country: on the one hand, further development and improvement of national languages, and on the other hand, an increase in the importance of the Uzbek language as a state language is taking place.

In childhood, bilingualism (bilingualism) is formed in the life of a child, instead of the capture of each language, depending on what situations and to what extent he uses bilingualism. In preschool age, the following specific cases of bilingualism formation can be indicated:

- the child is brought up from the moment of birth in a bilingual family in the context of being treated from one language to another;
- the child speaks the mother tongue in the family, and outside of it (with neighbors, relatives and other persons) Masters the other language;
- the child occupies a different language in a preschool educational institution in specific goal-oriented activities and in addition to them.

According to psycholinguistic literature, true bilingualism only develops if a person is able to express any thought in at least one language in a suitable way. If speech is not fully formed in any language, then the structure of thought will break down, and the desire to express one's opinion will fail, which will lead not only to psychological oppressions, but also to deep losses in the quality of communication and loss of a person's personality. Such a phenomenon, called semilingualism, in general, is also much more dangerous for society, since a certain part of its members cannot control their emotions and bring their own feelings, needs, desires into Word form in an appropriate way. If a person cannot say what he wants, he will be unable to compete on an equal footing with others, use the usual forms of communication, and he will be forced to resort to some other form of self-government, and sometimes use violence, force. It follows

from this that it is necessary to properly organize the correction of the speech development of the individual from an early age. The first start also has a positive effect on the adoption of the native language and the subsequent acquisition of any other language. "The earlier the language is occupied, the easier and more fully the knowledge is acquired," notes I. Jinkin.

The child is considered a social being from the moment of birth. Its social development at each age stage has its own characteristics, task and content, creating the appropriate conditions for work in the field of pedagogy for the implementation of which darkor.

Communication with the child should be built on the basis of cooperation with him. The fact that adults constantly force something forms in the child not an active desire to research and know, but a sluggishness, just a desire to adapt to the environment.

Between the ages of one and three, the social situation regarding the development of the child changes significantly. Together with their loved ones, adults, other adults (employees of preschool institutions, an assistant educator) begin to enter the child's circle of communication, who must first of all satisfy the little one's need for attention and care. In such conditions, children at an early age develop a need to communicate with adults about things, toys and actions that must be performed with them.

A child at this age develops the ability to establish emotional and practical relationships with adults, which helps him to adapt to new life conditions: correctly accept thoughts that assess words, requests, and emotional relationships of other people.

In children three to five years old, the need for the affection of adults, their understanding and communication with him is preserved. Communication based on trust in adults and its emotional state (joy, pleasure, sadness, calmness, irritability, etc.k.) develops the ability to feel, to understand the reasons for the change in mood. A new form of communication with adults – communication on interesting topics-arises and develops. He initially focused on joint cognitive activities with adults (e.g. game, experimenting with objects and toys, making something out of paper and natural material, etc.) are fused, and then, by the end of the fifth year of the child's life, have the appearance of "theoretical" communication on cognitive topics unrelated to a particular situation.

Fluency in language as a means of communication implies: the presence of certain and theoretical knowledge of language; the ability to compare language tools with communication tasks and conditions, that is, with the situation; the ability to organize speech communication taking into account the social norms of behavior; knowledge of the national characteristics of language tools. All this ensures the communicative competence of the individual, which is determined by the ability of the individual to solve one or another communicative tasks in various areas and situations of communication with the help of language tools. From this it can be said that communicative competence is the integral unity of two components – linguistic and social, the connection of a certain amount of linguistic and social knowledge with communication skills and skills.

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